

Synthesis of Substituted Ureas and Thio-ureas.

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Weith (*Ber.*, 1876, 9, 820) and all other workers after him obtained sym-di-derivatives by heating together urea and the amines at 170° or above, the only experience to the contrary being that of Fleicher (*Ber.*, 1879, 9, 995) who obtained mono-phenyl urea from urea and aniline. Our object was to establish the condition under which *mono*-substituted products would be produced in good yield.

It is now recognised that in the case of urea all the reactions indicated below are *reversible* (cf. Davis and Underwood, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2595).

1. $\text{NH}_2\text{N}:\text{CO} \rightleftharpoons \text{NH}_2 + \text{HN}:\text{CO} \rightleftharpoons \text{NH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}_2$,
2. $\text{HN}:\text{CO} + \text{NH}_2\text{R} \rightleftharpoons \text{NH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR} \rightleftharpoons \text{NH}_2 + \text{RN}:\text{CO}$
3. $\text{RN}:\text{CO} + \text{NH}_2\text{R} \rightleftharpoons \text{RNH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR}$.

The reaction between urea and the amines is thus primarily dependent on the "urea dearrangement" (equation 1). Phosphoric oxide was chosen as the condensing agent as it was expected that it would accelerate the dearrangement by removing the ammonia from the zone of action. This expectation was amply realised; for in the presence of phosphoric oxide reaction took place at temperatures as low as 105—115°, and 66 to 88 per cent. of the urea was converted.

Disubstituted ureas are formed by the breaking up of the mono-derivative into the corresponding isocyanate. Davis and Underwood (*loc. cit.*) showed that mono-phenyl urea breaks up in this way at 168°. The low temperature used in our experiments explains why the mono-derivatives were produced in good yield. This desideratum was further achieved by using an excess of urea, so that very little of the amine was available for the third reaction.

When the investigation was extended to thio-urea, a higher temperature (170°) was found necessary and considerable hydrogen sulphide was given off during the process. *o*-Toluidine and *p*-toluidine gave *mono*-substituted thio-ureas, while *m*-toluidine did not give any thio-urea derivative at all. This shows that at the temperature of the experiment thio-urea has the diamide structure and that the equations are similar to those in the case of urea.

By heating thio-urea and aniline in the presence of phosphoric oxide a small amount of mono-phenyl urea was obtained. The thio-urea undoubtedly acted partially in its ψ -form, yielding phenylguanidine, which broke up into ammonia and phenylurea. It might be interesting to recall in this connection the work of Hans Krall (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1897) who maintains that guanidine decomposes into carbon dioxide and ammonia, and not into urea and ammonia. Obviously this is not so in the case of phenylguanidine.

When urethane and aniline were refluxed with phosphoric oxide in xylene solution, diphenyl urea was obtained exclusively and in good yield. Thio-urethane also acted in the same way. The urethane probably breaks up into alcohol and isocyanic acid thus:

and the latter reacts with aniline according to reactions 2 and 3 already formulated. Here the phosphoric oxide accelerates the 'dearrangement' of the monophenyl urea first formed into phenyl isocyanate and this explains why the di-derivative is formed to the exclusion of the mono-substituted product. It remains to refer to the preparation of di-butyl urea by Dixon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1895, 67, 556) who obtained it by heating together butylamine and urethane at a temperature as high as 220°.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Aniline and Urea.—Urea (4 g.) and aniline (5 c. c.) were heated together with phosphoric oxide (2 g.) at 110° for 2 hours. The mass was cooled, washed first with water and then with benzene, and recrystallised from alcohol when fine needles of mono-phenyl urea, m. p. 146°, were obtained (yield 2.5 g.)¹. (Found: N, 20.7. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 20.5 per cent). On recrystallising from acetone a condensation product, m. p. 222.5°, was obtained. (Found: N, 15.45. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$ requires N, 15.9 per cent.).

*o-Toluidine and Urea.*²—These were heated together in molecular proportions in presence of the requisite amount of phosphoric oxide at 115-20° for 2 hours. The product was purified as before and recrystallised from absolute alcohol; m. p. 182-3°. (Found: N, 18.8. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 18.7 per cent.).

¹ Fleischer (*loc. cit.*) obtained mono-phenyl urea by heating aniline and urea at 150-170°. Weith (*loc. cit.*) and Baeyer (*Annalen*, 1864, 131, 252) obtained the di-derivative at 160-190°. Davis and Underwood obtained both mono- and di-derivatives.

² Davis and Underwood obtained *o*-tolyl urea by heating at 160° for 7 hours.

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*m-Toluidine and Urea.*⁵—*m*-Toluidine (7 c.c.), urea (19 g., nearly 4 equivalents) and phosphoric oxide (3 g.) were heated at 120-125° for 4 hours. The product was cooled, washed with cold water and then extracted with boiling water. From the filtrate on keeping overnight 1.5 g. of *m*-tolylurea separated out; m. p. 141-4° (crystallised from absolute alcohol). Reported m. p. 142°. Mixed m. p. with urea 112°.

The insoluble residue was crystallised from rectified spirit; yield 4 gms. M. p. 225°. (Found: N, 11.5. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2O$ requires N, 11.7 per cent.). Thus in this experiment 65-70% of the urea was converted. *m*-Toluidine (8 c.c.) urea (5 g., in equivalent amounts) and phosphoric oxide (2.5 g.) were heated at 115° for 2 hours. Only the di-derivative was obtained. The same amounts when heated at 105° for 1½ hours, gave, in addition to the di-derivative, a solid, m.p. 125° (crystallised from absolute alcohol). This has not been identified, and the yield was very poor.

*p-Toluidine and Urea.*⁶—Toluidine (4 g.), urea (3 g.) and phosphoric oxide (2.3 g.) were heated at 110-115° for 3 hours. Cooled and washed thoroughly with cold water. The residue was repeatedly extracted with the minimum amount of absolute alcohol. From these alcoholic extracts *p*-tolyl urea (2 g.), m.p. 178-4°, was isolated. (Found: N, 18.8. Calc. N, 18.6 per cent.).

The portion insoluble in alcohol was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid (in which it is very sparingly soluble, when di-*p*-tolyl urea (2.7 g.), m.p. 252°, was obtained. Melting points reported in literature are 244°, 256° and 263°. (Found: N, 11.4. Calc. N, 11.7 per cent.).

Phenetidine and Urea.—Phenetidine (4 g.) was heated with the equivalent amounts of urea and phosphoric oxide at 120° for 4 hours. The product was washed with ice-cold water (slightly acidified) and extracted with very dilute alcohol. The filtrate was concentrated and *p*-ethoxy-phenyl urea or dulcin (1.9 g.) separated out. Crystallised from water and obtained as fine needles; m. p. 159-61°.

The insoluble residue was crystallised from glacial acetic acid and 2.5 gms. of sym-di-ethoxy-phenyl urea, m. p. 220-23°, were obtained.

Urethane and Aniline.—Equivalent quantities of urethane and aniline were refluxed with phosphoric oxide in xylene solution at 140-5° for 2 hours. The xylene was then distilled off and the residue

⁵ No reference in the literature. It is obvious that *m*-toluidine does not react in the absence of a condensing agent, and that the monosubstituted product is not obtained unless the urea is in excess.

⁶ Davis and Underwood obtained the di-derivative at 160°.

washed with acidulated water. The crude residue melted at 244-5° and was therefore practically pure diphenylurea. On crystallising from absolute alcohol the m.p. rose to 245-6°.

Thio-urea and Aniline.—Thio-urea (4 g.) aniline (5 c. c.) and phosphoric oxide (2.3 g.) were heated at 140° for 3 hours when hydrogen sulphide was evolved. The mass was cooled and extracted with water, and the aqueous solution concentrated. Fine radiating needles separated out of the solution. This was crystallised from 50 per cent spirit; m.p. 145°-6°. This was identified to be mono-phenyl urea by a mixed m.p. with a sample prepared from aniline and urea.

The portion insoluble in water was crystallised repeatedly from rectified spirit, but a pure product could not be isolated. The substance melted at 125-35°. (Found: N, 13.65 per cent.). It also contains sulphur and phosphorus and was not identified.

o-Toluidine and Thio-urea.—Heated at 170° for 4 hours. Extracted with water and from the filtrate a compound, m.p. 90-32°, was isolated. This has not been identified, but seems to be a urea derivative. It does not contain sulphur.

The insoluble oily layer was induced to crystallise and *o*-tolyl-thio-urea was obtained. Crystallised from dilute spirit; m.p. 160°. (Found: N, 17.46. Calc. N 16.9 per cent.).

p-Toluidine and Thio-urea.—The usual procedure was followed but there was no evolution of H₂S. No definite compound could be isolated from the aqueous extract of the reaction product. The insoluble matter was crystallised several times from absolute alcohol m. p. 172°. Recorded m. p. of *p*-tolyl thiourea is 188° (182° ?) and that of the di-*p*-tolyl compound, 176°. The analysis, however, proved it to be *p*-tolyl thiourea. (Found: N, 16.88. Calc. N 16.87 per cent.).

Thio-urethane and Aniline.—Thio-urethane was prepared by passing NH₃ into an alcoholic solution of potassium hydroxide and carbon disulphide. The product was triturated with sufficient warm water and the substance crystallised from alcohol when shining white feathery crystals of diphenyl thiourea, m.p. 148°, were obtained. Reported m.p. 158°.

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